

DEVELOPMENT OF TRANSLATORS' LINGUISTIC GUESSING ON ENGLISH CLASSES

Marina Vinnikova¹, Aliya Abdrakhmanova^{2*}, Natalia Pashkovskaia³, Olga Strelkova⁴

¹PhD, Assoc. Prof., Kazan Federal University, Russia, marinaissaeva@mail.ru

²PhD, Assoc. Prof., Kazan Federal University, Russia, z_aliya@mail.ru

³PhD, Assoc. Prof., Moscow International University, Russia, n.pashkovskaia@inbox.ru

⁴PhD, Assoc. Prof., Moscow Pedagogical State University, Russia, olga-strelkova20@mail.ru

*Corresponding author

Abstract

This article is devoted to the process of students' linguistic guessing development on English language classes at the university. The problem is not new, but it is a strategic direction in improving the quality of translators' training. There is a growing need for highly qualified and professionally competent translators to be able to understand the information presented in authentic, up-to-date, constantly updated texts sources in foreign languages.

The system of educational and professional exercises is used as the main tool. This system is represented by three types of exercises (formal speech operational exercises, training-communicative exercises, real-communicative exercises). They contribute to the development of three levels of linguistic guessing: purely linguistic guessing, contextual-linguistic guessing, and contextual-discursive guessing.

Development of the ability to guess the meaning of a word based on its internal (linguistic) and external (contextual) supports plays a leading role in creating a potential vocabulary for translators. The process of the linguistic guessing development requires a systematic approach when using information and communication technologies and building pedagogical interaction between a teacher and students on a subject-subject basis. Using a system of educational and professional exercises aimed at developing the linguistic understanding translators, as well as the creation and expansion of a "database" of lexical standards in the long-term memory of students, will allow you to achieve the desired results faster and more efficiently.

Keywords: foreign language, higher military school, didactic principles, language guessing, system of educational and professional exercises

1. INTRODUCTION

The current stage of higher school development is associated with improving the quality of training specialists. There is a growing need for highly qualified and professionally competent specialists, who are able to understand the information presented in authentic, up-to-date, constantly updated texts sources in

foreign languages.

Despite the development of some perspectives on the problem of the linguistic conjecture, translators still make little use of its capabilities in practice. In addition, the teaching methodology of foreign languages at university, as a rule, is rarely focused on the linguistic conjecture development. This problem has practically not been developed and is the reason for dissatisfaction of translators by the results of foreign language training, the inability of university graduates carry out effective foreign language communication in the course of professional activities.

2. METHODOLOGY

The purpose of the article is to develop a system of educational and professional exercises aimed at developing language guess skills for translators. Research methods: analysis of literary sources on the research topic, study and generalization of University practice, observation, questionnaires, interviews and surveys.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this scientific work, linguistic guess is understood as the intellectual ability to reveal the meaning of an unfamiliar word, taking advantage of the context (Nurtdinova, Vinnikova, etc, 2022, p. 16).

In the process of learning a foreign language, translators have to make predictions about the meaning not only of a single word, but also of a whole sentence, as well as a connected text. Therefore, based on our experience, we propose the structure of the guess, which differs from a traditional one: a purely linguistic guess, contextual-linguistic guess and contextual-discourse guess (Nurtdinova, Vinnikova, etc, 2022; Tsukanova 2004).

To develop language guesswork among translators, a system of educational and professional exercises is used. It is understood as a certain sequence of communicative speech actions that occurs in the order increasing complexity of structural and content organization (Isaeva 2017, Blagoveshchenskaya, Ainoutdinova etc 2022). When building a system of educational and professional exercises, the following didactic principles are used:

The principle of communicativeness is implemented by approximating the process of development of translators' linguistic conjecture in foreign language classes to the real process of professional communication (Carton, 1985).

The principle of the dominant role of exercise in all areas of language learning is associated with the need to create speech stereotypes, which are based on the exercise, since strong skills and abilities in using foreign language as means of communication are created because of repeated repetition of the same speech units or combinations (Markina, 1997).

The principle of integrativeness involves the integration of knowledge from various academic disciplines (foreign language, speech culture), simultaneous development of both communicative and professional communication, academic and social skills.

In this study, educational and professional exercises constitute one of the important parts of development work linguistic guesswork and expansion of translator's potential vocabulary.

The educational material for the exercises is selected in such a way that, in addition to language knowledge, it conveys such information on professional topics and thereby contributes to the professional growth of translators, developing their outlook and logical thinking, causing them interest in the discipline, positive emotions, which contribute to better mastery of a foreign language.

The system of educational and professional exercises identifies three types of exercises aimed at developing language skills guess of translators:

1. Formal speech operational exercises aimed at developing purely linguistic guesswork.
2. Educational and communicative exercises aimed at developing contextual linguistic guesswork.
3. Real-life communicative exercises aimed at developing contextual-discursive

guess (Nurtdinova, Vinnikova etc, 2022, p. 56).

Formal speech operational exercises are receptive in nature. They help to develop guess skills of the word

meaning by its internal supports (form). In addition, they help to identify and remove many possible difficulties in the linguistic conjecture development. These exercises are performed strictly given algorithm.

Educational and communicative exercises are reproductive in nature. They help to develop guess skills of the word meaning based on external supports (context), the ability to predict the content of a particular sentences based on language experience.

Real communication exercises do not have an unambiguous algorithm and this does not limit the actions of translators. On the contrary, they can widely vary depending on the composition of the group, the experience of communicative activity, level of linguistic conjecture development, individual typological characteristics of students' data. The exercises are aimed at developing productive language guess. They help to develop skills of carrying out transformation, transformation of syntactic structures (collapse and expansion), skills of predicting and anticipating the likely development of the text.

To develop purely linguistic guess, exercises like matching are used (correlating lists of Russians and foreign words, correlation of words and their meanings; antonyms, synonyms of foreign words and their definitions, grouping words by parts of speech), multiple choice (multiple choice exercises), crosswords, defining (define words/ phrases), guessing (from the description, guess what is being said), flash cards (vocabulary cards with new words and terms from the text; composing sentences using these words-terms), reading (try to understand the meaning of the highlighted words in context, check yourself in the dictionary; read the text with new words-terms, study the contexts of use of new words, draw up a content plan using these words).

To develop contextual linguistic guesswork, exercises such as matching are used (correlating expressions; choosing the correct translation of each term from the proposed equivalents, composing sentences from halves;), multiple choice (multiple choice exercises), cloze, puzzles, multiple matching, true / false, gap filling (omissions of expressions, words, prefixes, suffixes, dialogues with selective answers, placement in a sentence terms suitable in meaning), translating (translation of sentences taking into account the peculiarities of translating grammatical constructions: passive voice, gerund, participial and infinitive phrases, modal verbs, conditional mood).

To develop contextual-discursive guess, exercises such as cloze (banked, elide), dialogue with freely constructed answer, finding and correcting errors in statements, sequencing, sentence completion; substitution (replacing highlighted words and expressions in the displayed text), insert a sentence, put sentences into the right order (text construction), separate the two mixed-up texts, gapped summary, sequencing.

In the process of developing linguistic conjecture, the following difficulties may arise: different levels of development of linguistic guess; insufficient inclusion of students in this process; difficulties in providing motivation; negative

opinion of one of the students about the lesson.

The effectiveness of managing the process of developing the language guesswork of translators depends on the following: indicators: 1. Speed and quality of learning material by students. 2. Motivation for cognitive activity, interest in knowledge among translators. 3. Objectivity in assessing the mastery of educational material. 4. Active management of the cognitive activity of translators without the direct participation of the teacher. 5. Prompt awareness of students and teachers about the progress of mastering didactic material.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Development of the ability to guess the meaning of a word based on its internal (linguistic) and external (contextual) supports plays a leading role in creating a potential vocabulary for translators. Process the development of linguistic conjecture requires a systematic approach when using information and communication technologies and building pedagogical interaction between a teacher and students on a subject-subject basis. Using a system of educational and professional exercises aimed at developing the linguistic understanding of translators, as well as the creation and expansion of a "database" of lexical standards in the long-term memory of students, will allow you to achieve the desired results faster and more efficiently.

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